

THE ADVANTAGES OF USING MODULAR TECHNOLOGIES AT PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Problem statement. In the modern information society, when technologies require the new system of thinking, school should teach students communication skills, the ability to work with any information and to think flexibly, depending on a situation. Therefore, modern primary school teachers must possess innovative teaching technologies that requires a school reform according to the State National Program “Education” (Ukraine XXI century) [8] the National Doctrine for Development of Education in Ukraine [9], the Conception of Continuous Pedagogical Education [1], the National Standard of Primary Education [2], the Regulations on Distance Learning [7].

The use of distance learning modular technologies in all areas of educational activity requires from a modern pedagogical higher education institution the creation of appropriate conditions for forming readiness of future primary school teachers for distance learning in a lifelong education system. In our study, we define primary school teachers’ readiness for DL as possession of knowledge

ABSTRACT

The modern information society raises new requirements to the process of training of a future primary school teacher as a component of a lifelong education system. An important role in providing of lifelong learning is given to distance education, which promotes self-motivation and self-actualization, enhances independent cognitive activity, and contributes to the acquisition of fundamental knowledge and the formation of skills to use it in professional activity.

and skills to study in a lifelong education system.

Recent studies analysis. The analysis of recent studies and publications, in which the attempts to solve to the problem are found, shows that modern scholars pay much attention to the introduction of distance learning into the educational process , particularly in the process of continuous education of primary school teachers.

The problem of primary school teachers training for professional activity in the modern information society was studied by V. Bondar, N. Bibik, M. Hordiichuk, O. Kyvliuk et al.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the content of the course “Fundamentals of Distance Learning in Primary Education” which is taught to future primary school teachers in a lifelong education system

Main material statement. The learning technologies that are based on information and pedagogical technologies change the

functions of a future primary school teacher in the educational environment of universities, increase the requirements for knowledge, skills and personal qualities. Therefore, great importance is attached to the questions of forming students' readiness to solve learning and self-study tasks, search, analyze, and present the necessary information using computer tools and technologies. There are objective reasons for the formation and development in a future specialist structural components of learning activity (learning tasks, learning actions, reflection, control), psychological readiness (activity, motivation to self-study, interest in educational and professional activity) and competence in information and communication technologies.

The main objective of the course is to train future professionals for the successful use of distance learning technologies in a system of lifelong education of primary school teachers.

In accordance with the goal and objectives of the course "Teaching future primary school teachers to train students on the basis of modular technologies" and considering the complex of requirements for a primary school teacher in the DL [1], we formulated the requirements for knowledge and skills of future primary school teachers that should be acquired and practised in the process of mastering the discipline.

On learning theoretical material of the course, a future primary school teacher must know:

–nature, kinds, functions, tasks, models and technologies of DL on the modern stage;

–development of DL in pedagogical theory and practice;

–conditions of organization of DL in a pedagogical higher education institution; – requirements for the use of DL technologies;

–basic principles of DL in a system of lifelong education of primary school teachers;

–forms and methods of organizing DL in a system of lifelong education of primary school teachers.

On completing the tasks for practical classes and independent work, a future primary school teacher should be able to:

–be familiar with DL models and technologies;

–work with a web-site of lifelong education of primary school teachers;

–organize and conduct DL in a system of lifelong education of primary school teachers;

–develop distance learning courses for primary school teachers, including such elements as forms, glossary, tests, etc.;

–create electronic didactic tools using hypertext, multimedia technologies and technologies of Web 2.0;

–search and select information on the Internet.

The content of the course "Fundamentals of Distance Learning in Primary Education" is determined in accordance with the goal and objectives of the course. The structure of the course consists of two modules.

Module 1 includes two content modules which reflect the topics of lectures, practical classes and independent work (see Table 1)

Table 1. Structure of the Course

Topic	Hours											
	Full-time						Correspondence					
	Total	incl.					Total	incl.				
		l	p	lab.	ind.	i.a.		l	p	lab.	ind.	i.a.
Module I												
Content Module 1. Theoretical Fundamentals of Distance												
Topic 1. Distance Learning in Modern Educational Environment	8	2	2		2	2	8	2			3	3
Topic2. Organization and Holding Training of DL at a University	8	2	2		2	2	8	2			3	3
Content Module 2. Technology of Distant Learning in Primary Education												
Topic 3. Main Competecies of a Primary School Teacher Required for DL	8	2	2		2	2	8	2			3	3
Topic 4. Didactical Foundations of DL Organization in Primary Education	8		2		3	3	8				4	4
Topic 5. Ways of Support of DL in Primary Education	10		2		4	4	10		2		4	4
Topic 6. DL Organization in a System of Lifelong Education of Primary School Teachers	12		2		5	5	12		2		5	5
Total Module I	54	6	12		18	18	54	6	4		22	22

The modular control has two components: the control of the independent practical assignments completion and taking tests.

In the first case, students load on the distance course webpage completed practical assignments in the form of files; a lecturer checks these works, assesses and analyzes,

and then sends the results to students for revision or rewriting if necessary.

Tests are carried out on all topics. Each student, taking a test on any topic, has one attempt and 8 min. to complete it, after he or she can see the number of correct answers and earned points.

In the distance course “Fundamentals of Distance Learning in Primary Education” tests

on each topic consist of 10 questions developed in a closed form: select one or several answers.

4. The Final Testing. The goal of this stage is to test and evaluate the knowledge and skills of the course as a whole. During this stage, students take closed-form tests, consisting of 15 questions. To complete the test they have only one attempt.

5. Conclusions, analysis and reflection. This stage combines two complementary processes:

the analysis of a student's activity by a lecturer and by other students, reflection (the analysis of their own activities) students. The teacher concludes the study of the distance course, examines the activity of students, and calculates the final score.

Conclusions. Thus, the analyzed training course "Teaching future primary school teachers to train students on the basis of modular technologies" takes into account the following peculiarities of the DL organization in a system of lifelong education of primary school teachers: the shift from teaching to independent cognitive activity of students; the necessity of forming abilities of

distance interaction by means of information technologies (compulsory computer literacy of teachers and students); the change of interaction between the subjects of educational activity caused by the advent of information technologies which leads directly to changes in the educational process; flexibility where residence and class hours do not matter, since the classes can be conducted at time and place convenient to everyone.

We believe that this training course contributes to fundamentalization of education, the development of systems thinking of future specialists, the study of theoretical, methodological and practical problems of forming, functioning and development of a lifelong education system, building readiness of future specialists for DL in a lifelong education system.

Prospects for further studies are in improving the course "Teaching future primary school teachers to train students on the basis of modular technologies" in all forms of organizing the educational process of a pedagogical higher education institution by means of modern DL technologies.

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